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Research Article

**OCCURRENCE OF IATROGENIC NEEDLE PRICK INJURIES
TO THE BOTH MALE AND FEMALE DOCTORS**¹Sajjad Tassawar, ²Rana Muhammad Farooq Sattar, ³Muhammad Haji¹Nishtar Medical University, Multan., ²Nishtar Medical University, Multan., ³Independent Medical College, Faisalabad.**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: This research's main objective was to determine the occurrence of iatrogenic injuries to doctors caused by needles during various procedures.

Place and duration of study: the study was conducted from January 2020 to March 2020 in 3 months in various hospitals in Multan.

Material and methods: This research involved a total of 125 patients. In this report, both female and male doctors were included. To gather the details, a pre-designed proforma was used, and later analysis was performed using SPSS. After clarification of the report, informed consent was taken from all the candidates. The approval of the Ethical Committee was taken.

Results: The mean age was 34 years. While doing work, 61 out of 125 doctors suffered needle injuries. Of these 61 doctors, 19 were postgraduate trainees, and 42 were house officers. House officers were 82 out of 125 doctors, while postgraduate trainees were 43. Of 82 house officers, 23 (18.4 per cent) confirmed that no proper instruction or safety precautions were taught to prevent needle injury. Needle injuries were seen while operating in 61 (48.8 per cent) of the patients. 19 (15.2 per cent) were among these postgraduate trainees, while 42 house officers were (33.65 per cent).

Conclusion: House officers sustain more injuries at the beginning of the training due to lack of knowledge of safety measures and proper handling of needles and equipment.

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INTRODUCTION:

Needlestick injury is characterised as a poke sustained by someone stained with body fluids or blood with a needle. In 2007, the World Health Organization (WHO) published around 2 million needle-induced injuries during various procedures. Around 5.6 million employees, either due to percutaneous accidents or workplace hazards, are vulnerable to bloodborne illnesses. There are typically no immediate signs after needle-induced injuries, but they are responsible for the transmission of various forms of viruses, including Hepatitis B (HBV), Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), and Hepatitis C (HCV). Data from the WHO in 2000 showed that there were approximately sixteen thousand cases of hepatitis C, one thousand cases of HIV and sixty-six thousand cases of hepatitis B due to needle pinching. Twenty-five different types of bloodborne diseases transmit these forms of injuries. Health professionals who work in operating theatres, wards and outdoor units, etc., mostly suffer these accidents. Nevertheless, people from other occupations, including miners, tattoo artists or farmers, may also experience such injuries.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This research involved a total of 125 patients. In this report, both female and male doctors were included. To gather the details, a pre-designed proforma was used, and later analysis was performed using SPSS. After clarification of the report, informed consent was taken from all the candidates. The approval of the Ethical Committee was taken.

RESULTS:

The mean age was 34 years. While doing work, 61 out of 125 doctors suffered needle injuries. Of these 61 doctors, 19 were postgraduate trainees, and 42 were house officers. House officers were 82 out of 125 doctors, while postgraduate trainees were 43. Of 82 house officers, 23 (18.4 per cent) confirmed that no proper instruction or safety precautions were taught to prevent needle injury. Needle injuries were seen while operating in 61(48.8 per cent) of the patients. 19 (15.2 per cent) were among these postgraduate trainees, while 422 house officers were (33.65 per cent).

DISCUSSION:

According to our study findings, 48.8 per cent (61) of doctors have experienced needle injuries. Various reports suggest that most health practitioners are vulnerable to needle injuries. Different incidence rates have been shown in various studies, such as 68 per cent in Jordan, 30 per cent in Turkey, and 74 per cent in South Korea. According to our report, in 15.2 per cent (19) postgraduate trainees and 33.65 per cent (42)

house officers, injuries caused by needles were seen. Despite proper training and education, this very high incidence of needle injuries means that health practitioners must take adequate infection prevention care. There were some restrictions in our research, such as a limited number of doctors and the absence of para-medical personnel. To examine the issue and then set the necessary guidelines to avoid these accidents and minimise the risk of bloodborne diseases, a broad study involving all health professionals such as nurses, waste management workers, operating theatre attendants and medical technicians must be undertaken.

CONCLUSION:

House officers sustain more injuries at the beginning of the training due to lack of knowledge of safety measures and proper handling of needles and equipment.

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